

Molecular iodine-catalyzed reactions toward the synthesis of bis-indoles under microwave irradiation in the absence of solvent

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Microwave-induced molecular iodine-catalyzed reaction of indole with carbonyl compounds in the absence of any solvent has been performed to prepare bis(indolyl)methanes. This reaction is extremely fast and produces products in good yield. An electrophilic route is described to explain the formation of the products.

Keywords: Microwave, solventless, molecular iodine, bis-indoles.

Introduction

Indoles are extremely important molecules that have a variety of medicinal properties¹. Preparation of indole derivatives is an important goal. Many studies have been performed for the synthesis of bis(indolyl)alkanes. In general, acids are required to prepare these compounds. To overcome the limitations of acid-induced reactions, a few other methods are developed. To prepare bis(indolyl)methanes indoles it is established that electrophilic substitution reaction is necessary. Many reagents and catalysts are discovered to accomplish this goal. Some of them include indium trichloride^{2a}, indium triflate^{2b}, indium fluoride^{2c}, acetic acid^{2d}, lithium perchlorate^{2e}, cupric bromide, ferric chloride^{2f}, N-bromosuccinimide^{2g}, CAN^{2h} and clay²ⁱ.

Results and discussion

In previous publications, our groups have demonstrated molecular iodine-catalyzed reactions³. These reactions have proven useful for the preparation of interesting organic compounds. Microwave-induced reactions are highly compatible in the presence of iodine. We report here molecular iodine-catalyzed microwave-induced reaction for the preparation of

bis(indolyl)methanes. This method is simple and high yielding (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. A simple route for the synthesis of bis-indolylmethane under microwave irradiation.

Reaction of indole **1** with aldehyde **2** in the presence of 0.1 equivalent of molecular iodine under microwave irradiation produced the bis-indole **3** in excellent yield. A thermal reaction of these two reactants takes much longer time for completion with significantly lower yield.

A number of aldehydes were used successfully to yield the products under microwave irradiation in the absence of solvent. The same reaction in an oil bath takes much longer with poor yield of the products (Table 1).

Indole **1** reacted with an activated diester **4** under identical conditions and produced product, a bis-indole **5** (Scheme 2 and Table 2).

Table 1

Entry	2		Thermal conditions			Microwave condition		
	R ¹	R ²	Time (h)	Catalyst (eq)	Yield (%)	Catalyst (eq)	Time (min)	Yield (%)
2a	H	Phenyl	1	0.1	40	0.1	2	80
2b	H	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	2	0.1	30	0.1	3	80
2c	H	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	1	0.1	45	0.1	4	80
2d	H	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	1	0.1	40	0.1	2	80
2e	H	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	2	0.1	40	0.1	2	70
2f	H	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	3	0.1	30	0.1	4	80
2g	H	Phenyl	1	0.1	40	0.1	2	75
2h	H	<i>n</i> -Pentyl	1	0.1	40	0.1	2	70

Table 2

Entry	Thermal			Microwave			
	Time (h)	Solvent	Catalyst Loading (eq)	Yield (%)	Time (min)	Catalyst% (eq)	Yield (%)
1	1	None	0.1	40	2	0.1	80
2	2	None	0.1	45	3	0.1	80
3	3	None	0.1	45	4	0.1	80
4	4	None	0.1	50	5	0.1	80
5	5	None	0.1	50	5	0.1	80

Scheme 2. A simple route for the synthesis of bis-indoylemethane diester under microwave irradiation.

The formation of bis-indoles can be explained through an electrophilic route that takes place at the C-3 center of the ring (path A). The intermediate **II** through an aromatization and protonation produces **III** through route B. Further protonation of the alcohol of the intermediate produces **IV** through route C and elimination of water produces a carbocation **V**. The reaction of the second molecules of indole takes place with the stabilized highly reactive carbocation **V** to produce product **3** (Scheme 3).

Experimental

To indole (1 mmol) was added the carbonyl compound (1.2 mmol) followed by a crystal of iodine (0.1 mmol). The reaction mixture was irradiated at a microwave oven at 50°C

A: Electrophilic Attack at C-3 Position of Indole
 B: Aromatization and protonation
 C: Protonation of Alcohol
 D: Dehydration
 E: Second electrophil substitution at C-3 position

Scheme 3. Proposed mechanism for bis-indoylemethane.

for a short period of time (see the Table). Dichloromethane (20 mL) was added to the reaction mixture and the contents were washed with aqueous sodium thiosulfate solution (5%, 5 mL), brine (5 mL), dried with sodium sulfate (2 g), and solvent was evaporated. The pure product was obtained

through a short column chromatography using ethyl acetate-hexanes as the solvent (20:80)⁴.

Conclusions

Molecular iodine-catalyzed reaction of indole with carbonyl compounds under microwave irradiation in the absence of any solvent produces bis-indole derivatives. The reaction is extremely rapid, economical and convenient to perform. In view of the importance of bis-indoles, this study can be expanded to use diverse carbonyl compounds and it is our expectation that novel heterocyclic compounds can be formed within a short time following environmentally benign conditions.

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4. The authors advised the researchers to conduct microwave-induced reactions in a well-ventilated hood in the event of leakage of radiation from the oven. It is important to state that the time required for the microwave-induced reactions may vary depending upon many parameters: different microwaves, solvent/solventless reactions, nature of the reactants, size and nature of the reaction vessels and location of the reaction mixture at the microwave oven (in the case of domestic microwave oven). It is confirmed that dipolar solvents or reactants can absorb microwave energy efficiently. This more polar reactants/solvents can accelerate a process. Moreover, microwave oven has its own "hot spots". The reaction can be accelerated if a reaction vessel is accidentally kept at a hot spot and irradiated. However, it is difficult to know the location of the hot spot. In some instances, differences of reactivity are noticed if a reaction mixture is placed inside the microwave oven at different locations: for example, at the middle part or at the side. Even a small change of solvent composition can accelerate or retard the reaction. A small structural change of the substrates can also affect the rate of the reaction. If the reaction is conducted in the absence of any solvent, an appropriate mixing of the reactants with the catalyst (or without the catalyst) is highly necessary. If the reactants are not properly mixed, certain amounts of these may decompose at high temperature or remain unreacted. The power level of microwave is an indication of energy and heat level. In general, reactions will be heated more if higher power level is used instead of lower power level even the solvent used has lower dipole moment. The heating power of microwave varies from one instrument to another, their sizes and also on the manufacturers. To obtain reproducible results, it is crucial to perform some known reactions and adjust the microwave power level accordingly. This type of observation should be considered when performing a reaction using a microwave oven.

